

First observation of
reactor
antineutrinos by
coherent scattering
with CONUS+

Nico Ackermann for CONUS+

Coherent elastic neutrino nucleus scattering

$$\frac{d\sigma(E_\nu, T)}{dT} \simeq \frac{G_F^2}{4\pi} \left[N - \underbrace{\left(1 - 4 \sin^2(\theta_W) \right)}_{\approx 0} Z \right]^2 F^2(q^2) M \left(1 - \frac{MT}{2E_\nu^2} \right)$$

Fermi constant
Weinberg angle
Form factor

Neutron number
Proton number
Kinematics term

- First predicted by D.Z Freedman in 1974
- First measured by COHERENT in 2017: CsI detector at pion-decay-at-rest source
- Measurement at nuclear power plant (was) still pending!

CEvNS cross section

**CEvNS cross section is large!
(For neutrino standards)**

**For Germanium:
 $N = 41 \rightarrow N^2 = 1681$**

**\rightarrow ~ 3 orders of magnitude
larger than for IBD!**

Typical neutrino experiments: Large target mass due to low cross sections

Super-Kamiokande

CONUS+:
Size $\sim 2 \text{ m}^3$
Active volume $\sim 4 \text{ kg}$

→ Possible due to
CEvNS channel!

Artificial neutrino sources

Reactors

First observation with CONUS+
 $E < 10 \text{ MeV} \rightarrow$ Fully coherent

Accelerators

First CEvNS observation (COHERENT)
 $E = 20 - 50 \text{ MeV} \rightarrow$ Partially coherent

Physics potential of CEvNS

BSM physics

Super Nova detection & modelling

Nuclear form factor & Weinberg angle

Neutrino floor for DM searches

CONUS collaboration

CONUS+ location

- Nuclear power plant in Leibstadt, Switzerland (KKL)
- Operational 11 months per year, with 1 month outage for reactor maintenance
- 20.7 m distance from reactor core
→ **neutrino flux: $1.45 * 10^{13} \bar{\nu}_e \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$**
- **Overburden: 7 – 8 m w.e.**
- **In reactor outage:**
drywell head placed above our room
→ additional overburden of 3.8 cm steel

CONUS+ shield

- Two layers of muon veto:
→ to account for higher muon flux compared to CONUS
 - Several lead layers for gamma suppression
 - Several PE (and borated PE) layers for neutron suppression
 - Flushing of detector chamber with radon-free air
- Total background reduction by 4 orders of magnitude

CONUS+ Ge detectors

- 4 point-contact high purity Ge detectors
(C5, C2, C3 & C4, + C1 at MPIK)
- Crystal/active mass:
4.0 kg / 3.74 kg
- Low energy threshold: ~ 160 eV
- Electrically cryocooled

Detector performance

Pulsar resolution < 50 eV (FWHM)

Trigger efficiency $\sim 100\%$ down to 150 eV

Low energy threshold $\rightarrow 160 - 180$ eV

Background model

Full decomposition of background up to 350 keV
for all detectors in on and off data

Result: First CEvNS detection at nuclear reactor

Number of CEvNS counts in combined fit
=
395 ± 106 counts

→ Rejection of null hypothesis at **3.7 σ**

→ **Consistent with SM prediction** within **0.5 σ**

Comparison to other CEvNS results

CONUS+ outlook - Detector upgrade and future analysis

- Run 2 data taking since beginning of 2025
- 3 new 2.4 kg PPC Ge detectors: C9, C7 and C6
Crystal mass: 4 kg → 8.2 kg

Significant improvement of result expected to be reached!

- PSD cut being studied for Run 2
- BSM analysis of Run 1 coming in the near future

Summary

- CONUS+ moved to KKL in Switzerland
- Start of physics data taking in Nov. 2023
 - **New location:** less overburden → adaptations on shield and background model
 - **Detector upgrade:** improvement in energy resolution and trigger efficiency
 - Remote control of data acquisition
- **First detection of CEvNS at reactor site:**
 - Total exposure: 347 kg d ON, 60 kg d OFF
 - Observed: **395 ± 106 neutrinos** (SM: 347 ± 95)
 - Rejection of null hypothesis: **3.7 sigma**

BACKUP

Background Model C2

Component	Contribution ON [counts/d/kg]	Contribution OFF [counts/d/kg]
Muons	16.5 +- 0.3	16.4 +- 0.3
Neutrons	21.6 +- 3.1	17.7 +- 2.5
Muon-induced neutrons in overburden	2.2 +- 0.1	1.8 +- 0.1
Cu parts	4.4 +- 0.4	4.4 +- 0.4
Pb210 in cryostat	< 0.1	< 0.1
Pb210 in shield	0.1 +- 0.02	0.1 +- 0.02
Ge cosmogenics	0.2 +- 0.02	0.2 +- 0.02
Metastable Ge states	0.1 +- 0.01	0.1 +- 0.01
Radon	2.8 +- 0.1	0.7 +- 0.1
Kr85	< 0.1	< 0.1
H3	1.3 +- 0.2	0.5 +- 0.2
Xe135	0.1 +- 0.01	< 0.1
Leakage component	3.0 +- 0.5	3.0 +- 0.5
Total	52.3 +- 3.3 (DATA = 50.7 +- 1.2)	45.1 +- 2.7 (DATA = 45.3 +- 1.3)

Experimental approach

Consequences of cross section

$$\sigma \sim N^2 E_\nu^2$$

Maximize E_ν

BUT: Coherency condition!

$$E_\nu \leq \frac{1}{2R_A} \approx \frac{197}{2.5 \sqrt[3]{A}} \text{ [MeV]}$$

$\approx 20 \text{ MeV (Ge76)}$

→ **Partially** vs **fully coherent** experiment
→ Complementary!

Maximize N

BUT: Maximum recoil energy

$$E_{rec}^{max} = \frac{2 \cdot E_\nu^2}{m_n \cdot A + 2 \cdot E_\nu} \approx \frac{2 \cdot E_\nu^2}{m_n \cdot A}$$

Higher recoil energy → Higher energy signals

→ Easier to measure

Quenching of CEvNS signal

CEvNS interaction in Germanium → recoil of Ge nuclei

BUT: The observable of the CEvNS process is only the part of the energy that turns into ionisation of atoms in the Ge crystal lattice
(Other part goes into phonons/heat → not measurable by our detectors)

$$\text{Quenching factor} = \frac{E_{\text{ion}}}{E_{\text{rec}}}$$

Energy dependent!

Knowledge of quenching factor is crucial for the signal prediction!

→ Very important systematic, but previously very large uncertainties for $E_{\text{rec}} < 10 \text{ keV}$

→ Dedicated quenching measurement by CONUS

Result consistent with Lindhard theory
with $k = 0.162 \pm 0.004$

Background characterisation: Results

Gammas

Muons

Muon rate in CONUS+ room:
(107 ± 3) counts/s/m²

→ factor 1.9 reduction
compared to outside

→ 7.4 m w.e. overburden

Neutrons

Energy region	ϕ (cm ⁻² (GW h) ⁻¹)
Thermal	172.1 ± 16.3
intermediate	91.6 ± 6.3
Fast + cascade	1.0 ± 0.8
Total	264.7 ± 13.2

Installation of CONUS+

CONUS in KBR completed. Ge refurbishment

Dec 2022

Apr 2023

KBR dismantling. KKL on site preparations

Detector tests at MPIK. Final installation campaign

Jul 2023

Aug 2023

Commissioning

Nicola Ackermann - NuPhys 26

First physics run started

Nov 2023

First reactor off data produced

May 2024

Detector swap

Nov 2024

Background Model C3

Component	Contribution ON [counts/d/kg]	Contribution OFF [counts/d/kg]
Muons	16.5 +- 0.3	16.4 +- 0.3
Neutrons	21.6 +- 3.1	17.7 +- 2.5
Muon-induced neutrons in overburden	2.2 +- 0.1	1.8 +- 0.1
Cu parts	3.6 +- 0.4	3.6 +- 0.4
Pb210 in cryostat	< 0.1	< 0.1
Pb210 in shield	0.1 +- 0.02	0.1 +- 0.02
Ge cosmogenics	0.2 +- 0.02	0.2 +- 0.02
Metastable Ge states	0.1 +- 0.01	0.1 +- 0.01
Radon	2.6 +- 0.1	0.7 +- 0.1
Kr85	< 0.1	< 0.1
H3	1.3 +- 0.2	0.5 +- 0.2
Xe135	0.1 +- 0.01	< 0.1
Leakage component	0.8 +- 0.2	0.8 +- 0.2
Total	49.3 +- 3.1 (DATA = 48.8 +- 1.2)	42.2 +- 2.7 (DATA = 42.5 +- 2.0)

The final CONUS result

Predecessor of CONUS+

Data collection from 2018 – 2022
at KBR power plant (Brokdorf, Germany)

Detector	Signal prediction	Likelihood fit constraint (90% CL)
C1	41 +- 8	< 47
C2	26 +- 5	< 67
C4	23 +- 5	< 79
All	91 +- 10	< 143

→ Factor ~ 1.6 (90% C.L.) above SM prediction

KBR was shut down permanently in 2021
→ Search for a new location

Phys. Rev. Lett. **133**, 251802 (2024)

Background characterization of location

Done in preparation for move to Leibstadt

- Gamma measurement with HPGe detector (CONRAD)
- Neutron measurement with Bonner Sphere Array
- Environmental parameters (Radon, temperature ...)
- Cosmic muons with liquid scintillator
- Wipe tests to measure surface contamination
- Vibrations with piezoelectric sensors

arXiv:2412.13707

Detector upgrades compared to CONUS

Refurbished crystals after dismanteling in KBR:

- ASIC based electronics
 - Improve trigger efficiency at low energies
- Large reduction of point contact size and use of bonding techniques for contacting
 - Reduction of electronic noise
 - Substantial improvement of trigger efficiency, energy resolution, and noise edge

Non-linearity in energy calibration

Cosmogenic components - Muons

Data without muon veto: ca. 99% muons

→ Use this to get "baseline" for muon simulations

Muon flux in room: $(53 \pm 1) \text{ muons } s^{-1} cm^{-2}$

→ consistent with expected overburden

To this we apply a factor accounting for the muon veto efficiency

Factor:

99% at higher energies, but energy dependence at very low E

Muon tagging inefficiency at very low E

Simulations show that at very low E (< 400 eV) 80% of muon-induced signals in the crystals come from muons that don't cross any muon veto plate!

This induces “inefficiency” in the muon veto system because not all of these events will be tagged by the veto!

→ Efficiency at low E modeled with polynomial (i.e. 97% < 400 eV)

Cosmic neutrons

- Typical cascade peak at 100 MeV
- Not very well distinguishable from reactor neutrons due to very low flux and degeneracy in response functions of Bonner spheres
- Had to be simulated with model of reactor building and neutron flux from literature
- Result: 0.9 ± 0.2 neutrons/d/cm² in [20, 1000] keV
 - Small flux but not completely suppressed by overburden
 - Important impact on CONUS+ background model

Cosmogenic components – Neutrons

Initial cosmic neutron spectrum
with $0.014 \text{ neutrons/s/cm}^2$

→ Cosmic neutrons in room:
 $0.9 \pm 0.2 \text{ neutrons/d/cm}^2$

→ $21.6 \pm 3.1 \text{ counts/d/kg}$ in $[0.4 - 1 \text{ keV}_{ee}]$
($50.3 \pm 7.2 \%$ of C5 background)

Radon in detector chamber

Stability plots show:

Radon greatly reduced by flushing,
but lines still visible

→ High impact in [100,400] keV

→ Small impact in ROI

Experimental differences in ON vs OFF times

2 key differences:

1. Placement of drywell lid above room in OFF

→ 19% reduction in cosmic neutron flux in room

→ 3% reduction of muon flux

2. Better radon flushing in OFF

→ ca. factor 7 reduction of radon contribution in OFF

→ also reduction of inert gases in detector chamber

Reactor correlated backgrounds:

Neutrons:

Impact < 1% of background in all energy regions

No evidence of ^{16}N , small impact of inert gases from reactor

All effects considered in the Bkg model

Data processing

Overview of applied cuts

1. Rejection of time periods:

- High radon level (no flushing)
- High noise rate (due to grounding problems → exclusion of C4)
- Instabilities in noise peak
- Periods with more microphonic events
- Period of reactor shutting off/turning on

2. Applied cuts to data

- Muon veto anticoincidence cut with time window of 450 μs
- TRP cut: remove events immediately after pre-amplifier reset (window: 500 – 2000 μs)
- Microphonic cut
- Anticoincidence cut between detectors

Induced dead times

- Muon veto dead time = veto rate * time window
- TRP dead time = TRP rate * time window
→ cuts are correlated: overall dead time = 11%-13%
- DAQ dead time: lost events during saturation and trigger holdoff
→ dead time < 2%

Overall live time during Run 1:

ON: 119 d

OFF: 19 d

Data stability

Excellent data stability reached during the whole run!

Rate in radon line (C2)

Trigger efficiency parameters

Data stability in CONUS+ Run1

More stability plots

Signal prediction

Data driven spectrum based on method proposed by the Daya Bay collaboration

Detector	Threshold [eV _{ee}]	Predicted CEνNS counts
C5	170	116 (+20/-18)
C2	180	96 (+16/-14)
C3	160	135 (+23/-20)
COMBINED	-	345 (+34/-30)

**Due to very low detector thresholds
→ increased impact of smaller neutrino energies**

Likelihood analysis

- Fit both reactor ON and OFF spectrum
- **Inputs:** Data (including live time and dead times), background model, predicted signal spectrum, measured trigger efficiency values, measured detector resolution, active volumes, neutrino flux at CONUS+ location

Parameter	Number of parameters per detector	Pull terms?
Signal strength s	1	No
Neutrino flux	1	Yes
Background scaling b	1	Yes
Trigger efficiency	2	Yes
Quenching uncertainty	4	Yes
Energy calibration uncertainty	1	Yes

Comparison with other result – CONUS

- Constraints from CONNIE, TEXONO, vGen
- Colaresi et al, PRL 129, 211802 (2022)
 - “...very strong preference... for the presence of ... CEvNS ...”
 - Signal prefers low energy excess of quenching factor as compared to Lindhard quenching to be consistent with SM

Comparison with other results – CONUS+

